

Synthesis of 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-1-substituted phenyl isoquinoline and 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-1-substituted benzyl isoquinoline

Susanta Kr. Borthakur^a and Birendra N. Goswami^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Handique Girls' College, Panbazar, Guwahati-781 001, Assam, India

^bFormerly of the Synthetic Organic Chemistry Division, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006, Assam, India

E-mail : drbngoswami@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 1 December 2006, accepted 20 July 2007

Abstract : Isoquinoline derivatives are obtained from amides using AlCl₃-KI in acetonitrile solvent. This cyclo dehydrating Lewis acid produced no side product and yield is above 95% isoquinoline derivative at room temperature.

Keywords : Isoquinoline derivatives, dehydrating agent, Lewis acid catalyst.

Morphine is an alkaloid produced from poppy plant *Papaver somniferum* as an active ingredient. Although it is a potent analgesic¹, its use is limited because of several side effects. A great number of morphine analogues have been synthesized by varying the substituents in the morphine nucleus. Grewe² *et al.* prepared a new class of synthetic analgesics known as the morphinanes. Dextromethorphan, (3-methoxy, 17-methyl-(9 α ,13 α ,14 α)-morphinan), have been the subject of considerable interest for the past few years due to their analgesic and extremely important bronchodilating^{3,4} agent.

Results and discussion

In this paper the synthesis of 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-1-(substituted phenyl)isoquinoline and 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-1-(substituted benzyl)isoquinoline from *N*-2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl substituted phenyl acetamide and *N*-2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl substituted phenyl amide respectively by the intramolecular cyclization (Bischler-Napieralskie reaction) has been reported. Dextromethorphan is prepared from *N*-[2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl]-4-methoxy phenyl acetamide. The conventional method to this cyclization used the hazardous and corrosive reagents like phosphorous oxychloride, phosphorous pentoxide etc. But here a new catalyst of Lewis acid type i.e. AlCl₃ with KI in acetonitrile solvent for this reaction step has been used. This cyclo dehydrating Lewis acid produced no side product and yield is above 95% isoquinoline derivative at room temperature. The synthetic sequence leading to the formation of title compounds taking 2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethylamine (**1**) and phenylacetic acid as the starting material are outlined in Scheme 1.

The literature on cyclization of *N*-[2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl]-1-substituted phenyl acetamide to 3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-1-substituted benzyl isoquinoline is scanty⁵⁻⁷. Literature reports show that the amide is treated with phosphorous oxychloride in benzene or amide is treated with phosphorous pentoxide in warm benzene to form cyclized product. But the major drawback of these methods is that heating is essential and benzene a health hazard chemical is used as solvent along with phosphorous oxychloride. Although in recent years the versatility of AlI₃ has been demonstrated⁸ but the chemistry of AlCl₃ in presence of KI is less explored^{9,10}. Here we utilize AlCl₃/KI in acetonitrile as a mild, efficient and versatile dehydrating agent for the intramolecular cyclodehydration of amides to isoquinolines, which are the intermediates for antitussive drug dextromethorphan and its analogue. These compounds were synthesized by the following procedure.

To a mixture of anhydrous AlCl₃ (0.01 mol) in dry acetonitrile (50 ml) KI was added (0.04 mol) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere for 1 to 1.5 h. To this reaction mixture *N*-[2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl] substituted phenyl acetamide (0.01 mol) was added and stirred for 8 h at room temperature. The progress

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 3a-f and 4a-c

Compd.	R	Yield (%)	Mol. formula (M ⁺)	Analysis (%) : Found (Reqd.)		
				C	H	N
3a		90	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N (211)	85.12 (85.31)	7.91 (8.06)	6.51 (6.64)
3b		92	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ NCl (245.5)	73.14 (73.32)	6.72 (6.52)	5.61 (5.70)
3c		95	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ NCl ₂ (280)	64.50 (64.29)	5.49 (5.36)	4.87 (5.00)
3d		90	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ (256)	70.59 (70.31)	6.10 (6.25)	11.05 (10.94)
3e		92	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ NO (227)	79.21 (79.30)	7.67 (7.49)	6.00 (6.17)
3f		95	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO (241)	79.54 (79.67)	8.10 (7.88)	5.70 (5.81)
4a		96	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ (270)	70.94 (71.11)	6.42 (6.67)	10.52 (10.37)
4b		91	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO (255)	79.79 (80.00)	8.46 (8.24)	5.67 (5.49)
4c		94	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ NO (241)	79.39 (79.66)	8.09 (7.88)	5.49 (5.71)

of the reaction was monitored by TLC. On completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and water was added to the reaction by cooling the same to 0–5

Table 2. IR and ¹H NMR spectral data of the compounds 3a-f and 4a-c

Compd.	IR (KBr, ν cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃ , δ = 0 ppm)
3a	1655, 3060	0.63–2.10 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.23 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 6.75–7.68 (5H, m, Ar-H)
3b	1652, 3090	0.81–2.21 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.28 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 6.90–7.20 (5H, m, Ar-H)
3c	1652, 3085	0.72–1.92 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.30 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 6.82–7.20 (3H, m, Ar-H)
3d	1655, 3100	0.76–2.10 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.25 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 6.76–7.25 (4H, m, Ar-H)
3e	1652, 3075	0.82–2.12 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.32 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 5.85 (1H, s, OH), 6.72–7.30 (4H, m, Ar-H)
3f	1655, 3080	0.90–2.10 (10H, m, -CH ₂), 3.30 (2H, t, N-CH ₂), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.65–7.22 (4H, m, Ar-H)
4a	1650, 3070	1.10–1.70 (12H, m, methylene-CH ₂), 3.36 (2H, s, benzylic-CH ₂), 6.78–7.20 (4H, m, Ar-H)
4b	1652, 3080	1.23–1.70 (12H, m, methylene-CH ₂), 3.16 (2H, s, benzylic-CH ₂), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.48–6.92 (4H, m, Ar-H)
4c	1654, 3085	1.20–1.67 (12H, m, methylene-CH ₂), 3.20 (2H, s, benzylic-CH ₂), 5.50 (1H, s, OH), 6.78–7.12 (4H, m, Ar-H)

°C and then treated with 30% ammonia solution. This was then extracted with ethylacetate and the organic layer was washed with 10% sodium thiosulphate solution, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get the desired product 3a-f and 4a-c in 95% yield. The structure of the compounds 3a-f and 4a-c were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR and mass) data. The IR spectra (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) of the compound did not exhibit absorption due to carbonyl and NH groups. The ¹H NMR spectra of 3a-f revealed proton signal for five CH₂ groups at δ 0.63–2.21 ppm as multiplet, one CH₂ at C-3 position as triplet at δ 3.28 ppm and for aromatic protons as multiplet at δ 6.65–7.75 ppm respectively. The IR spectra (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) of the compounds 4a-c exhibited absorption at 1640, 1450 and 3000 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra of 4b in CDCl₃ showed multiplet at δ 1.23–1.70 ppm due to methylene protons, singlet at δ 3.16 ppm due to benzylic CH₂ proton, δ at 3.50 (3H, s) ppm for OCH₃ and at 6.48–6.92 ppm for aromatic protons respectively. Mass spectra of compound 4b showed molecular ion peak corresponding to molecular weight of 255 (Tables 1 and 2).

Experimental

M.p.s were determined on a Buchi apparatus. Mass spectra were recorded with a LC-MS Bruker (Model esquire 3000) mass spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer system-2000 FT IR spectrometer and ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian T-60/90 MHz spectrometer. Commercially available anhydrous aluminium chloride and potassium iodide (Aldrich) were used directly. Acetonitrile was used after distillation over phosphorus pentoxide. Amides were prepared following standard procedures.

Typical procedure: Anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.133 g, 0.001 mol) and potassium iodide (0.664 g, 0.004 mol) was added to dry acetonitrile (30 ml) and the mixture stirred magnetically at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere for 1 to 1.5 h. To this reaction mixture was added *N*-[2-(1'-cyclohexenyl)ethyl] phenyl amide (**2a**) (0.229 g, 0.001 mol) and stirred for 8 h at room temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. On completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and water was added to the reaction by cooling the same to 0–5 °C and then treated with 30% ammonia solution. This was then extracted with ethylacetate (2 × 50 ml) and the organic layer was washed with 10% sodium thiosulphate solution, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get the desired product **3a** at 90% yield. The structure of the compounds **3a** assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and spectroscopic (IR, ^1H NMR and mass) data. The IR spectra (KBr , $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the compound did not exhibit absorption due to carbonyl and NH groups. The ^1H NMR spectra of **3a** revealed proton signal for five CH_2 groups at δ 0.63–2.21 ppm as multiplet, one CH_2 at C-3

position as triplet at δ 3.23 ppm and for aromatic protons as multiplet at δ 6.75–7.68 ppm respectively. The IR spectra (KBr , $\nu\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the compounds **3a** exhibited absorption at 1655 and 3060 cm^{-1} . Mass spectra of compound **3a** showed molecular ion peak corresponding to molecular weight of 211. Similarly, other compounds **3b-f** and **4a-c** were prepared (Tables 1 and 2).

Acknowledgement

We thank the Director, RRL, Jorhat for providing the facilities to carry out this research work.

References

1. A. F. Casy and R. T. Parfitt, "Opioid Analgesics", Plenum Press, New York, 1986, Ch. 10.
2. R. Grewe, *Naturwiss.*, 1946, **33**, 333; R. Grewe and A. Mondon, *Chem. Ber.*, 1948, **81**, 279.
3. A. I. Meyers and Thomas R. Bailey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **51**, 872.
4. M. Kitamuna, Yi Hsiao, R. Noyoni and H. Takaya, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28**, 4829.
5. Michael Hanack and Hans Joerg Schneider, *Chem. Abst.*, 1965, **63**, 11383.
6. O. Schneider and A. Grussner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1951, **34**, 2211.
7. Su Dong Cho, Deok-heon Kweon, Young-Jin Kang, Sang-geyong Lee, Woo Song Lee and Young-Jin Yoon, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1999, **36**, 1151.
8. "Dictionary of Inorganic Compounds", Chapman & Hall, London, 1992, Vol. 1, p. 36 and references cited therein.
9. M. Node, T. Kajimoto, K. Nishide, F. Fujita and K. Fuji, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 219.
10. M. Node, K. Ohta, T. Kajimoto, K. Nishide, E. Fujita and K. Fuji, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Jpn.*, 1983, **31**, 4176.